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One-particle density matrix polarization susceptibility tensors

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The electric field-induced change in the one-electron density has been expressed as a series of the one-particle density matrix susceptibilities interacting with the spatial distribution of the electric field. The analytic approximate expressions are derived at the Hartree-Fock theory, which serves as a basis for the construction of the generalized model that is designed for an arbitrary form of wavefunction and any type of one-particle density matrix. It is shown that it is possible to accurately predict the changes in the one-electron ground-state density of water molecule in a spatially uniform electric field, as well as in spatially non-uniform electric field distribution generated by point charges. When both linear and quadratic terms with respect to the electric field are accounted for, the electric field-induced polarization energies, dipole moments, and quadrupole moments are quantitatively described by the present theory in electric fields ranging from weak to very strong (0.001–0.07 a.u.). It is believed that the proposed model could open new routes in quantum chemistry for fast and efficient calculations of molecular properties in condensed phases. © 2018 Author(s). All article content, except where otherwise noted, is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5051995>

I. INTRODUCTION

Molecular-level exploration of condensed phase phenomena becomes increasingly unavoidable as technology and medicine continue to develop. Unfortunately, the computational cost of accurate electronic structure calculations grows extremely fast with the number of particles, greatly limiting the use of the state-of-the-art first-principles theories when large and complex chemical systems such as solutions and biomolecules come into play.^{1,2} Due to this reason, it has been of particular importance nowadays to develop bridging theoretical techniques that link extremely accurate but localized pieces of information with certain knowledge of an atomistic organization and intermolecular interaction on relatively large spatial scales, typically ranging beyond few nanometers.

The development of hybrid methods such as the quantum mechanical-molecular mechanical (QM/MM) technique was a revolution in computational chemistry which allows insightful theoretical studies of quantum mechanical effects in biological systems because costly quantum mechanical calculations can be combined with lower-level and much less expensive classical dynamics.^{3,4} Combination of accurate *ab initio* methods with extensive experimental and semi-empirical refinements led to the development of a wide variety of force fields,⁵ whereas sophisticated partitioning of the Hamiltonian or electron density enabled numerous schemes for efficient fragmentation within a QM level.⁶

However, even with the modern advances in computational chemistry, accurate description of phenomena due to complex heterogeneous molecular environments remains a challenge in the following areas: (i) describing the electronically excited states (electronic solvatochromism)^{7–10} and (ii) understanding the vibrational properties of molecules in ground and electronically excited states (vibrational or vibronic solvatochromisms).^{11–13} The interface between QM and MM levels is usually realized by electrostatic embedding and only rarely the Pauli exclusion principle and dispersion are additionally included.¹⁴ Unfortunately, it is quite difficult to efficiently treat the environment-induced potential operator due to the complicated nature of intermolecular interactions that theoretically cannot be solely envisioned as a sum of separate contributions coming from electrostatic, dispersion, and Pauli effects.¹⁵ For example, one of the most frequently used, efficient, and reasonably accurate *ab initio* fragmentation methods, the effective fragment potential (EFP) methods, is limited to the Hartree-Fock (HF)^{16,17} or density functional theory (DFT) levels.^{18–20} While they can approximately describe the environment composed of molecules in their ground states, they cannot be used for highly correlated wavefunctions such as electronically excited states. In such cases, the full QM method needs to be utilized on the excited state wavefunction, which is embedded within the EFP environment through the electrostatic or polarizable embedding.²¹

Most of the efforts to theoretically treat extended molecular aggregates are rooted in energy-based philosophy. However, in the past two decades, there has been considerable interest in density-based approaches of a wider scope and aim.^{22–28} In particular, the importance of one-electron

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densities in chemistry is well known and acknowledged in the community,^{22,29,30} though obtaining the accurate electron density distribution has been an unresolved issue for most of the chemical systems in condensed phases. Given that fact, it would be incredibly insightful to establish a first-principles connection between the one-particle density and the perturbation in the environment through the introduction of *density matrix susceptibility* (DMS) tensors. The main postulate of the present work is that the associated change in the one-particle density matrix, $\delta\mathbf{D}$, can be represented in a product form of the generalized perturbation susceptibility \mathbf{B}_i and the environment-induced perturbation on a molecule, $\delta\mathbf{P}_i$, evaluated at a certain site i ,

$$\delta\mathbf{D} \approx \sum_i^{\text{Sites}} \mathbf{B}_i \cdot \delta\mathbf{P}_i,$$

where the “ \cdot ” symbol denotes the inner tensor (dot) product. While $\delta\mathbf{P}_i$ contains critical information about the actual distortion of the electronic cloud, perturbation susceptibility is assumed to be a property of unperturbed molecules and is to be precomputed only once. Thus, such DMS could be adapted into an efficient effective one-electron fragment potential which in principle is applicable to an arbitrary level of theory, as long as the one-particle densities are available by means of quantum chemistry methods. It also means that such a technique would dramatically reduce the cost of quantum chemistry calculations because the task of performing full computation on a molecular aggregate would reduce to much simpler matrix operations.

The simplest type of perturbation, yet the most relevant for chemistry, is the electrostatic perturbation. It is worth mentioning that, at the moment, there is no simple *ab initio* method to compute polarization-induced electron deformation densities without considering the entire molecular aggregate by using full quantum chemistry calculations.^{26,31,32} In this work, we explore the susceptibility of the molecule’s electronic density to polarize due to external electrostatic perturbation from first principles. The deformation density is expressed in terms of the one-particle density matrix polarization susceptibility tensors that are properties of isolated molecules and can be extracted from quantum chemistry calculations. The focus on the density (matrix) instead of the energy (scalar) is beneficial since it provides the directional tensor description of the polarization that could be combined with other effects such as Pauli repulsion or dispersion,²⁶ in contrast to the standard interaction energy approaches. We show that accurate polarization of the one-particle density matrix is achievable and can be realized as long as the one-particle density matrices are available. It is believed that the proposed method could be a basis for a construction of an alternative approach in fragment-based modeling of extended molecular aggregates that is not limited to the ground state chemistry.

The necessary theory and the derivation of the *ab initio* density matrix susceptibility model at the HF approximation¹⁶ are elaborated in Sec. II. Subsequently, this model serves as a basis for generalization to the arbitrary one-electron density with electronic correlation which is derived in Sec. II. The implementation details in a computer code as well as the

validation procedures are detailed in Sec. III. The performance of the models is then discussed in Sec. IV. Finally, in Sec. V the presentation is concluded with a few remarks for future development.

II. THEORY

The electronic energy of a closed-shell molecule is given by the time-independent Schrödinger equation,

$$E^{(0)} = \langle \Psi^{(0)} | \mathcal{H}^{(0)} | \Psi^{(0)} \rangle, \quad (1)$$

where E stands for the total electronic energy, Ψ the electronic wavefunction, and \mathcal{H} the Hamiltonian operator. In the above, the superscript (0) denotes the reference or unperturbed state that is assumed to be known. Under the influence of an external electrostatic perturbation, the total electronic energy becomes

$$E[\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r})] = \langle \Psi | \mathcal{H}^{(0)} + \mathcal{V}(\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r})) | \Psi \rangle \quad (2)$$

in which $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r})$ is a non-uniform electric field distribution. The electric field-induced energy change is an unknown functional of the associated change in the one-electron density,

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}) = 2 \sum_{\alpha\beta} D_{\alpha\beta} \phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_{\beta}^*(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3)$$

In Eq. (3) $\phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r})$ is a basis function, which can be for instance an atomic orbital (AO) or a molecular orbital (MO), and $D_{\alpha\beta}$ is the corresponding one-particle density matrix. If perturbation-independent basis is chosen, the electric field-induced change in the one-particle density is given by

$$\delta\rho(\mathbf{r}) = 2 \sum_{\alpha\beta} \delta D_{\alpha\beta} \phi_{\alpha}(\mathbf{r}) \phi_{\beta}^*(\mathbf{r}). \quad (4)$$

The electric field-induced change in the ground state’s one-particle density follows its energy minimum of the perturbed state. In addition, all the perturbed excited state one-electron densities must be excited state solutions of the Schrödinger equation with the exact energy-minimized ground state.

In the limit of a weak and spatially uniform electric field, the polarization-induced density matrix change of any electronic state or electronic transition is given by the following Taylor expansion:

$$\delta D_{\alpha\beta} = \left. \frac{\partial D_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \right|_{\mathbf{F}=0} \cdot \mathbf{F} + \frac{1}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 D_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial \mathbf{F} \otimes \partial \mathbf{F}} \right|_{\mathbf{F}=0} : \mathbf{F} \otimes \mathbf{F} + \dots, \quad (5)$$

where the “ \otimes ” symbol denotes the outer tensor product. In the above expression, the density matrix susceptibilities are simply equal to the derivatives of the density matrix with respect to the electric field (up to a multiplicative constant). In a general case, i.e., when the electric field is relatively strong and non-uniform, single-centered expansions, like the one from Eq. (5), are not sufficient enough to accurately describe the local polarization of electron density distribution.

The development of a general first-principles theory that is capable of accurately capturing the electric field-dependence of the one-particle density becomes extremely difficult. This is not only because of the very complicated (and generally

unknown) solution to the electronic correlation problem but also because a working model has to accurately predict all the n^2 elements of the density matrix where n is the size of basis set. Even relatively small errors in a particular matrix element will accumulate when performing two- and four-index contractions, and in turn, affect the evaluated properties with non-negligible errors.

Due to all of these reasons, the following approach is adopted here: a qualitative *ab initio* distributed-site model at the Hartree-Fock level of theory is developed first. Further on, we generalize it to an arbitrary level and type of the density matrix using the functional form that was found by considering the HF level as a guideline, but treating the density matrix susceptibility tensors as certain functions of adjustable parameters.

A. *Ab initio* density matrix susceptibilities: Hartree-Fock level

1. Induced dipole moment

$\delta\mathbf{D}$ from Eq. (4) should be directly related to the polarization-induced multipole moments because they are a measure of the distortion of the electron density distribution due to the external electric field. Therefore, as a starting point, the induced ground-state electronic dipole moment of a closed-shell molecule will be considered,

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\mu}(\mathbf{r}_Q) = 2 \text{Tr} \left[\delta\mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}_Q) \right], \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}_Q)$ is the atomic orbital (AO)-representation of the dipole moment operator defined with respect to the origin at \mathbf{r}_Q ,

$$\left[\mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}_Q) \right]_{\alpha\beta} = -\langle \alpha | \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_Q | \beta \rangle. \quad (7)$$

(In this work, the double struck font for matrices of vectors or higher-order tensors is used so that in this case \mathbb{M} can be considered as a $n \times n$ matrix of vectors of length 3). Note that if the total charge is conserved, the induced dipole moment is independent of the origin.

In the Hartree-Fock theory,¹⁶ \mathbf{D} is approximated as

$$\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{C}^\dagger, \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{C} describes the occupied molecular orbitals (MO's) as linear combinations of AO's, referred here to as the LCAO-MO matrix. \mathbf{D} is an idempotent matrix and if expressed in orthogonal basis the following holds:

$$\mathbf{D}^2 = \mathbf{D}. \quad (9)$$

The change in the molecular orbitals can be parameterized as suggested by McWeeny³³ by defining the idempotency-preserving variation

$$\delta\mathbf{C} = \boldsymbol{\Delta} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{(0)}, \quad (10)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$ is a square, non-singular, and non-symmetric matrix. McWeeny showed that

$$\delta\mathbf{D} = -\mathbf{D}^{(0)} + \left[\mathbf{D}^{(0)} + \mathbf{v} \right] \cdot \left[\mathbf{1} + \mathbf{v}^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{v} \right]^{-1} \cdot \left[\mathbf{D}^{(0)} + \mathbf{v}^\dagger \right], \quad (11)$$

where the auxiliary vector \mathbf{v} is defined as

$$\mathbf{v} \equiv \left[\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \right] \cdot \boldsymbol{\Delta} \cdot \mathbf{D}^{(0)}. \quad (12)$$

Expanding Eq. (11) in a Taylor series around $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$ and truncating it at linear terms with respect to $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$ gives

$$\delta\mathbf{D} \cong \left[\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \right] \cdot \boldsymbol{\Delta} \cdot \mathbf{D}^{(0)} + \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \cdot \boldsymbol{\Delta}^\dagger \cdot \left[\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \right] \quad (13a)$$

$$= \delta\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} + \mathbf{C}^{(0)} \cdot \delta\mathbf{C}^\dagger - \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \cdot \delta\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} - \mathbf{C}^{(0)} \cdot \delta\mathbf{C}^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{D}^{(0)}. \quad (13b)$$

The latter equality is true in a special case when the basis set functions are orthogonal, i.e., $\mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{(0)} = \mathbf{1}$. By substituting the McWeeny's result from Eq. (13a) into Eq. (6), one can show that

$$\frac{1}{4} \delta\boldsymbol{\mu}(\mathbf{r}_Q) \cong \Re \left\{ \text{Tr} \left[\delta\mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbb{L}(\mathbf{r}_Q) \right] \right\}. \quad (14)$$

In the above expression, the “ \Re ” symbol denotes the real part, and the intermediate quantity

$$\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{r}_Q) \equiv \mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot \mathbb{M}(\mathbf{r}_Q) \cdot \left(\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \right). \quad (15)$$

Note that $\mathbb{L}(\mathbf{r}_Q)$ contains the projector onto the unoccupied MO space at the absence of the external electric field. It means that the perturbed solution is constructed from the unperturbed virtual orbitals as well.

For the sake of simplicity, the orthogonality of AO's is assumed in this work, unless stated otherwise. It is proven in Appendix A that under such circumstances the induced dipole moment obtained in Eq. (15) is independent of the origin. This guarantees that the theory fulfills the total charge conservation requirement and, therefore, in the later course of the paper, the dipole origin will be omitted.

Although Eq. (14) is exact up to first order in $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$, it cannot be inverted at this moment to obtain $\delta\mathbf{C}$. If the orbitals are real, the analytic solution exists provided that the electric field is uniform. In a more general case, i.e., when the electric field is non-uniform, the analytic solution cannot be found without further approximations. Let the induced dipole moment be partitioned into separate contributions from the occupied localized MO's (LMO's), i.e.,

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\mu} = \sum_i^{\text{occ}} \delta\boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \quad (16)$$

where the induced dipole moment associated with the i th LMO is assumed to be linearly dependent on the local electric field, i.e.,

$$\delta\boldsymbol{\mu}_i \approx \boldsymbol{\alpha}_i \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i). \quad (17)$$

In Eq. (17), $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i$ is the distributed dipole-dipole polarizability tensor associated with the i th LMO, whereas $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i)$ is the electric field evaluated at the i th LMO charge centroid, $\mathbf{r}_i = \langle \phi_i | \hat{\mathbf{r}} | \phi_i \rangle$. By inserting the above result into Eq. (14), recasting the right-hand side in a matrix form and assuming real orbitals, one can separate the contributions coming from the occupied MO's as

$$\frac{1}{4} \boldsymbol{\alpha}_i \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i) = \delta\mathbf{c}_i^T \cdot \mathbf{L}_i. \quad (18)$$

Note that now $\mathbf{L}_i \equiv [\mathbb{L}]_i$ is a real rectangular matrix of dimension $n \times 3$ and $\delta\mathbf{c}_i$ is the i th column of the change in

the LCAO-MO matrix due to the polarization process. The solution for $\delta\mathbf{C}$ is

$$\delta\mathbf{c}_i^T = \frac{1}{4}\mathbf{F}^T(\mathbf{r}_i) \cdot \boldsymbol{\alpha}_i^T \cdot [\mathbf{L}_i]_{\text{Left}}^{-1}, \quad (19)$$

where $[\mathbf{L}_i]_{\text{Left}}^{-1}$ is a left inverse of \mathbf{L}_i matrix,

$$[\mathbf{L}_i]_{\text{Left}}^{-1} \equiv [\mathbf{L}_i^T \cdot \mathbf{L}_i]^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{L}_i^T \quad (20)$$

with the dimension of $3 \times n$. Note that the right inverse of \mathbf{L}_i does not exist because $\mathbf{L}_i \cdot \mathbf{L}_i^T$ is singular due to the fact that usually $n > 3$.

2. Density matrix change

Once the approximate relationship between the orbital change and the external electric field has been established in Eq. (19), one can obtain the final expression for the density matrix change that reproduces the induced dipole moment of the molecule. The change in the LCAO-MO coefficient is parameterized as

$$\delta C_{\alpha i} = \mathbf{b}_{\alpha}^{(i;1)} \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i), \quad (21)$$

where the susceptibility tensor is defined as

$$b_{\alpha;w}^{(i;1)} = \frac{1}{4} \sum_u^{x,y,z} [\boldsymbol{\alpha}_i]_{uw} [\mathbf{L}_i]_{\text{Left}}^{-1}]_{u,\alpha} \quad (22)$$

for $w = x, y, z$. The superscript “(1)” underlines the fact that the susceptibility introduced here is first-order with respect to the electric field. The result from Eq. (21) can be now inserted into the expression for $\delta\mathbf{D}$ from Eq. (13b) to finally give

$$\delta D_{\alpha\beta} \approx \sum_i^{\text{occ}} \mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;1)} \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i), \quad (23)$$

where the *density matrix polarization susceptibility tensor* is

$$\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;1)} = C_{\alpha i}^{(0)} \mathbf{b}_{\beta}^{(i;1)} + C_{\beta i}^{(0)} \mathbf{b}_{\alpha}^{(i;1)} - \sum_{\gamma} (D_{\alpha\gamma}^{(0)} C_{\beta i}^{(0)} + D_{\beta\gamma}^{(0)} C_{\alpha i}^{(0)}) \mathbf{b}_{\gamma}^{(i;1)}. \quad (24)$$

Hence, the three dimensional vector $\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;1)}$ describes the local linear polarization affinity of the density matrix element associated with the i th LMO centroid as well as the α th and β th orthogonal AO's. Transforming these vectors to a non-orthogonal AO basis is straightforward. It is emphasized here that all the elements of $\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;1)}$ are unique properties of electronically unperturbed molecules. However, they are valid only under the Hartree-Fock approximation, with a guarantee that only the overall charge (exactly) and the dipole moment (approximately, limited by the flavor of the distributed polarizability approximation), but not higher multipole moments and polarization energy, are correctly described.

Nevertheless, one very important feature of the susceptibility from Eq. (23) is that the density matrix increment is dependent only on the susceptibility element associated with the same pair of AO's. Therefore, there is no mixing in the AO's, rather the increment is proportional to the vector susceptibility, different for each density matrix element. This feature will be used to generalize the model to an arbitrary level of theory and order of electric field response in Sec. II A.

B. Generalized density matrix susceptibility model

1. Functional form of the model

Equation (23), which is the final result of Sec. II B, can be used as a guideline to construct a general model of density matrix polarization. Quadratic (and higher-order) terms with respect to the electric field can be added to the formulation, which leads to

$$\delta D_{\alpha\beta} = \sum_i^M \left\{ \mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;1)} \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i) + \mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;2)} : \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i) \otimes \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i) + \dots \right\}. \quad (25)$$

In the above equation, the density matrix susceptibilities $\mathbb{B}^{(i;R)}$, distributed over M sites, denote the R th order response with respect to the electric field. Note that $\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;1)}$ is a vector of length 3, whereas $\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(i;2)}$ is a 3×3 matrix. Also, the distributed expansion centers (labeled as i) are generalized to any point in the molecule. In principle, a slightly more general contribution due to the square of the electric field could be formulated here as $\sum_{ij}^M \mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(ij;2)} : \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i) \otimes \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_j)$, defining the second-order susceptibilities due to pairs of different sites i and j . However, in the present work such contributions are neglected and only “diagonal” susceptibilities (for simplicity denoted as $\mathbb{B}^{(i;2)}$ instead of $\mathbb{B}^{(ii;2)}$) are considered.

Equation (25) can refer to any type of one-particle density matrix such as a ground-state, excited-state, or transition density matrix. However, the exact mathematical form of the generalized density matrix susceptibilities from Eq. (25) is unknown.

2. Determining the generalized susceptibility tensors by linear regression

Let $\{\mathbf{F}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}), \mathbf{F}^{(2)}(\mathbf{r}), \dots, \mathbf{F}^{(N)}(\mathbf{r}), \dots\}$ be a set of N_{max} distinct and randomly sampled spatial distributions of the electric field. It is assumed that the exact difference one-particle density matrices (with respect to the unperturbed state) defined as

$$\delta\overline{\mathbf{D}}^{(N)} \equiv \overline{\mathbf{D}}^{(N)} - \overline{\mathbf{D}}^{(0)} \quad (26)$$

are known for each sample (the overline symbolizes the exact estimate). Now, for each pair of the AO indices, the following parameterization of Eq. (25) is constructed:

$$\delta D^{(N)} = \sum_i^M \left\{ \sum_u^{x,y,z} s_{iu}^{[1]} F_{iu}^{(N)} + \sum_u^{x,y,z} \sum_{w < u} r_{uw} s_{iww}^{[2]} F_{iu}^{(N)} F_{iw}^{(N)} + \dots \right\} \quad (27)$$

(the Greek subscripts were omitted here for notational simplicity). In the above equation, $B_u^{(i;1)} = s_{iu}^{[1]}$ and $B_{uw}^{(i;2)} = r_{uw} s_{iww}^{[2]}$, where r_{uw} is the symmetry factor equal to 1 for diagonal elements and 2 for off-diagonal elements of $B_{uw}^{(i;2)}$. The multiple parameter blocks ($\mathbf{s}^{[1]}$, $\mathbf{s}^{[2]}$, and so on) appear in the first power, allowing for linear least-squares regression. The square bracket superscripts denote the block of the parameter space.

To determine the optimum set, $\mathbf{s} = (\mathbf{s}^{[1]} \mathbf{s}^{[2]} \dots)^T$, a loss function Z that is subject to the least-squares minimization is defined as

$$Z(\mathbf{s}) = \sum_N^{N_{\max}} \left(\delta D^{(N)} - \overline{\delta D^{(N)}} \right)^2. \quad (28)$$

The Hessian of Z computed with respect to the parameters is parameter-independent (constant) and generally non-singular as long as the electric fields on all distributed sites are different. Therefore, the exact solution for the optimal parameters is given by the Newton equation

$$\mathbf{s} = -\mathbf{H}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{g}, \quad (29)$$

where \mathbf{g} and \mathbf{H} are the gradient vector and the Hessian matrix, respectively. The explicit forms of the gradient and Hessian up to second-order are given in [Appendix B](#). Note that in this case, the dimensions of parameter space for the block 1 and 2 are equal to $3M$ and $6M$, respectively.

III. CALCULATION DETAILS

The theory that is necessary to validate the density matrix susceptibility models from [Sec. II](#) was implemented in our in-house plugin to the Psr4 quantum chemistry program.³⁴ The water molecule was selected as a test system which was subjected to electrostatic perturbations due to random uniform electric fields and random collections of point charges generating non-uniform electric fields. Components of spatially uniform electric fields were determined from the uniform distribution in the interval of $|0.0404|$ a.u. generating an average field of 0.038 a.u. in an ensemble of 100 samples. Cartesian coordinates of point charges were drawn from the uniform distribution of a set of forty three-dimensional Euclidean points within a sphere of radius 6.0 bohrs with an origin that is located in the center of mass of the water molecule. In selection of random points, the space inside the union of spheres surrounding oxygen and hydrogen atoms with radii of 4.5 and 4.0 bohrs, respectively, was kept free from any point charges due to potential problems with the convergence of the self-consistent field (SCF) calculations. Electric charge values were selected from the one-dimensional uniform distribution in the interval of $|q_{\max}|$, where q_{\max} was tuned to obtain a desired ensemble of weak, moderate, and strong electric field magnitudes (with $q_{\max} = 0.05, 0.2, \text{ and } 0.4$ a.u., accordingly). In this way, independent sets of 100 random samples of either the uniform electric field or point charge distributions were selected and exact solutions of HF-SCF equations were performed for each validation procedure. In the case of non-uniform electric fields, the distribution centers of the *ab initio* DMS model [Eq. (23)] were assumed to be the LMO centroids (resulting in the five-center model), while the atoms were used for the generalized DMS models [Eq. (25), resulting in the three-center models]. This is because certain LMO centroids are often located at the same point which would introduce linear dependencies in the Hessian matrix from Eq. (B1) when using the generalized DMS scheme.

In order to validate all the models discussed in this contribution, the electric field-induced polarization energy, dipole moment, and quadrupole moment were analyzed in detail. The electric field-induced polarization energy at the HF level, δE^{Pol} , was computed from the following exact formula:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta E^{\text{Pol}}[\mathbf{F}] = & \text{Tr} \left\{ \mathbf{D}^{(0)} \cdot (2\delta\mathbf{J} - \delta\mathbf{K}) \right\} \\ & + \text{Tr} \left\{ \delta\mathbf{D} \cdot (\mathbf{H}^{(0)} + \mathbf{f}^{(0)} + 2\mathbf{V} + 2\delta\mathbf{J} - \delta\mathbf{K}) \right\}. \quad (30) \end{aligned}$$

In Eq. (30), $\mathbf{f}^{(0)}$ and $\mathbf{H}^{(0)}$ are the Fock matrix and the one-electron core Hamiltonian matrix of an unperturbed HF ground state, respectively, and \mathbf{V} is the one-electron external electrostatic potential matrix whereas $\delta\mathbf{J}$ and $\delta\mathbf{K}$ are the electric field-induced changes in the Coulomb and the exchange HF matrices due to the polarization of the electron density, respectively. In order to compare the performance of the usual distributed dipole-dipole polarizability approach,³⁵ the approximate interaction energy was also evaluated by using the expression

$$\delta E^{\text{Pol}}[\mathbf{F}] \approx -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i^{\text{occ}} \alpha_i : \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i) \otimes \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{r}_i), \quad (31)$$

in which α_i is the distributed anisotropic dipole-dipole polarizability tensor associated with the i th LMO centroid [see Eq. (17)]. The distributed polarizabilities were computed by utilizing the coupled-perturbed Hartree-Fock method.^{33,36} Orbital localization was performed by using the Boys method.³⁷

The electric field-induced dipole and primitive quadrupole moments were evaluated from the following expressions:

$$\delta \mu_u = 2 \sum_{\alpha\beta} \delta D_{\alpha\beta} \langle \alpha | u | \beta \rangle, \quad (32a)$$

$$\delta \Theta_{uw} = 2 \sum_{\alpha\beta} \delta D_{\alpha\beta} \langle \alpha | (u - u_{\text{CM}})(w - w_{\text{CM}}) | \beta \rangle, \quad (32b)$$

where the subscript ‘‘CM’’ denotes the center of mass of the water molecule. When the distributed polarizabilities were used instead of the polarization-induced difference density matrices, primitive induced quadrupole moments were computed from the induced dipole moments [given in Eq. (17)] according to

$$\delta \Theta = \sum_i^{\text{occ}} \{ \delta \mu_i \otimes (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_{\text{CM}}) + (\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}_{\text{CM}}) \otimes \delta \mu_i \}. \quad (33)$$

Primitive quadrupole moments were subsequently transformed to their traceless forms by

$$\delta \tilde{\Theta}_{uw} = \delta \Theta_{uw} - \frac{1}{3} \delta_{uw} \text{Tr} \Theta. \quad (34)$$

The methodology for the calculation of the electric field due to point charges can be found elsewhere.³⁸

To compute the interaction energy and the induced multipole moments, either exact or approximated forms of the difference density matrix from Eq. (5), Eq. (23), or Eq. (25) were used for a particular electric field distribution. The statistical evaluation of errors with respect to the benchmark (full HF calculations) was based on the following statistical quality descriptors:

1. Root Mean Square Energy (RMSE) Error

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\max}} \sum_N^{N_{\max}} \left(\delta E^{(N)} - \overline{\delta E^{(N)}} \right)^2}, \quad (35)$$

2. Root Mean Square Dipole (RMSD) Error

$$\text{RMSD} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\max}} \sum_N^{N_{\max}} (|\delta\boldsymbol{\mu}^{(N)}| - |\overline{\delta\boldsymbol{\mu}^{(N)}}|)^2}, \quad (36)$$

3. Root Mean Square Quadrupole (RMSQ) Error (RMSQ)

$$\text{RMSQ} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\max}} \sum_N^{N_{\max}} (|\delta\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}^{(N)}| - |\overline{\delta\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}^{(N)}}|)^2}. \quad (37)$$

The first describes the ability of the model to reproduce the exact energetics of the system, whereas the following two contain additional information on how well the deformation of the one-electron density is described. For Eqs. (36) and (37), the absolute magnitudes are defined as

$$|\boldsymbol{\mu}| = \sqrt{\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + \mu_z^2}, \quad (38a)$$

$$|\tilde{\boldsymbol{\Theta}}| = \sqrt{\tilde{\Theta}_{zz}^2 + \frac{1}{3}(\tilde{\Theta}_{xx} - \tilde{\Theta}_{yy})^2 + \frac{4}{3}(\tilde{\Theta}_{xy}^2 + \tilde{\Theta}_{xz}^2 + \tilde{\Theta}_{yz}^2)}. \quad (38b)$$

Throughout the work, the Hartree-Fock level¹⁶ was assumed and the 6-311++G** basis set³⁹ was used. Before all the calculations, the water molecule was energy-optimized with a maximum energy, a force, and displacement thresholds of 10^{-6} , 3×10^{-4} , and 1.2×10^{-3} a.u., respectively. For all the calculations of the density matrix polarization susceptibility tensors from Eqs. (23) and (24), the atomic basis was orthogonalized by using the Löwdin symmetric orthogonalization scheme⁴⁰ and was further back-transformed to the non-orthogonal AO basis. To compute the numerical first and second derivatives of the one-particle density matrix with respect to the electric field from Eq. (5), the following finite-difference formulae were utilized:

$$D_u = \frac{D(F_u) - D(-F_u)}{2F_u}, \quad (39a)$$

$$D_{uu} = \frac{D(F_u) + D(-F_u) - 2D^{(0)}}{F_u^2}, \quad (39b)$$

$$D_{uw} = \frac{D(F_u, F_w) + D(-F_u, -F_w) + 2D^{(0)}}{2F_u F_w} - \frac{D(F_u) + D(-F_u) + D(F_w) + D(-F_w)}{2F_u F_w}, \quad (39c)$$

where the subscripts $u, w = x, y, z$ on the right-hand sides denote the derivatives with respect to the Cartesian component of the electric field, and the finite difference steps $F_{u(w)}$ were assumed to be 0.0005 a.u. for all components.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Water molecule in spatially uniform electric field

Polarization under the uniform electric field is the simplest type of electrostatic perturbation whereby it is possible to compute the exact DMS according to Eq. (5) by using either the coupled-perturbed Hartree-Fock method³² or numerical differentiation. Here, the DMS's up to second order are considered, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(1)} = \left. \frac{\partial D_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \right|_{\mathbf{F}=\mathbf{0}}, \quad (40a)$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{\alpha\beta}^{(2)} = \left. \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 D_{\alpha\beta}}{\partial \mathbf{F} \otimes \partial \mathbf{F}} \right|_{\mathbf{F}=\mathbf{0}}, \quad (40b)$$

and electric field magnitudes in a range from very weak (<0.001 a.u.) to very strong (~ 0.07 a.u.). The *ab initio* model from Eq. (23) and the generalized model from Eq. (25) are also discussed for the sake of comparison. The associated error distributions in the prediction of polarization energies are shown in the scatter plot in Fig. 1, whereas the statistical performance descriptors of polarization energies and induced multipole moments are gathered in Table I.

All the tested models that are linear with respect to the electric field, i.e., from Eq. (23) (black solid squares in Fig. 1) as well as truncated at linear susceptibilities $\mathbb{B}^{(1)}$ from Eq. (5) (blue solid circles) and (25) (blue open circles), incorrectly reproduce the polarization energy. Interestingly, the predicted values are in strong correlation with the exact estimates and exhibit a similar slope of ~ 2 . Incorporation of the second-order term obtained either by numerical differentiation from Eq. (40b) (red filled circles) or by using the generalized DMS model (red open circles) dramatically reduces the errors leading to quantitative accuracy in all tested field magnitudes with the best RMSE of 0.173 kcal/mol ($R^2 = 99.1\%$) for the generalized DMS model. On the other hand, the induced dipole and quadrupole moments are reproduced reasonably well by using the first-order DMS with R^2 coefficients being greater than 97% in the case of dipole moments and from 69% up to 81% in the case of quadrupole moments. This

FIG. 1. Performance of the DMS tensors of the ground-state water molecule in uniform electric field. R_{\max} denotes the maximum rank of the electric field in the expansion from Eq. (25). Electric field magnitudes in a range from 0.0 to 0.07 a.u. were tested in 100 samples with randomly selected directions of the electric field.

TABLE I. Performance of the DMS tensors of the ground-state water molecule in uniform and non-uniform electric field^{d,a,b}.

		<i>Ab initio</i> DMS				Generalized DMS				Distributed polarizability		
		$R_{\max} = 1^c$		$R_{\max} = 1^d$		$R_{\max} = 2^d$		$R_{\max} = 1^e$		$R_{\max} = 2^e$		
Uniform electric field												
RMSE (kcal/mol)												
	4.041	(<i>n.d.</i>)	4.823	(<i>n.d.</i>)	0.231	(98.40)	5.0121	(<i>n.d.</i>)	0.173	(99.10)	0.112	(99.63)
RMSD (mD)												
	30.46	(97.91)	30.46	(97.91)	18.02	(99.27)	24.83	(98.61)	7.13	(99.89)	30.46	(97.91)
RMSQ ($\text{D}\text{\AA} \times 10^{-3}$)												
	47.89	(69.17)	39.24	(79.30)	8.56	(99.02)	37.63	(80.96)	3.94	(99.79)	50.66	(65.49)
Non-uniform electric field ^f												
RMSE (kcal/mol)												
W	0.067	(<i>n.d.</i>)	0.076	(<i>n.d.</i>)	0.003	(99.45)	0.004	(98.64)
M	1.072	(<i>n.d.</i>)	1.236	(<i>n.d.</i>)	0.057	(99.08)	0.070	(98.58)
S	4.220	(<i>n.d.</i>)	5.147	(<i>n.d.</i>)	0.402	(97.25)	0.332	(98.13)
RMSD (mD)												
W	3.36	(98.71)	1.03	(99.88)	0.94	(99.90)	3.36	(98.71)
M	14.72	(98.50)	7.72	(99.59)	4.55	(99.86)	14.72	(98.50)
S	44.80	(96.92)	33.06	(98.33)	15.96	(99.61)	44.80	(96.92)
RMSQ ($\text{D}\text{\AA} \times 10^{-3}$)												
W	6.22	(58.72)	1.59	(97.32)	1.42	(97.86)	5.45	(68.29)
M	28.22	(53.90)	10.45	(93.68)	5.68	(98.13)	23.94	(66.83)
S	78.07	(40.53)	43.33	(81.68)	14.40	(97.98)	64.33	(59.62)

^a R -squared coefficients are shown in parentheses. "*n.d.*" stands for "not determined."

^bRanks of the density matrix susceptibility models are denoted as R_{\max} where R_{\max} is the maximum power in the expansion from Eq. (25).

^c*Ab initio* HF model, Eq. (23).

^d*Ab initio* finite-difference model, Eq. (5).

^eLinear-regression generalized model, Eq. (25).

^f"W," "M," and "S" denote "weak," "moderate," and "strong" electric fields that are generated by sets of point charges, respectively (cf. Table II).

observation can be understood given the fact that the induced dipole and quadrupole moment is approximately proportional to the external electric field, whereas the polarization energy exhibits quadratic dependence [cf. Eq. (31)], hence the need of including at least quadratic terms in the expansion from Eq. (5) or Eq. (25).

In comparison to the dipole-dipole polarizability approach, quadratic DMS models perform only slightly worse (for example, RMSE = 0.173 and 0.112 kcal/mol when the generalized quadratic DMS model and the polarizability model are used, respectively). However, quadratic DMS models better

predict the induced multipole moments with R^2 systematically greater than 99%. Certainly, taking into account the distributed quadrupole polarizabilities would greatly reduce errors of the standard distributed polarizability approach. Nevertheless, it is clear that the second-order DMS models are quantitative even at very strong uniform electric fields.

B. Water molecule in spatially non-uniform electric field

To study the capability of the distributed DMS models to capture density matrix polarization in inhomogeneous electric fields, a water molecule surrounded by point charges is analyzed. Three different types of point charge environments that generate weak (0.003–0.007 a.u.), moderate (0.01–0.02 a.u.), and strong (0.02–0.05 a.u.) electric fields around the water molecule were considered (Table II) because similar ranges of the electric field are experienced by water molecules in liquid phase.^{41,42} Performance descriptors of the *ab initio* and generalized models of the density matrix susceptibility, as well as the conventional dipole-dipole distributed polarizability approach, are shown in Table I, whereas the error distributions in strong electric fields are additionally plotted in Figs. 2(a)–2(i).

TABLE II. Average electric fields in statistical sets of electrostatically perturbed ground states of water molecule surrounded by point charges^a.

Set ^b	Average electric field (a.u.)	
	Oxygen atom	Hydrogen atom
W	0.0046 ± 0.0019	0.0046 ± 0.0020
M	0.0184 ± 0.0075	0.0186 ± 0.0078
S	0.0368 ± 0.0150	0.0372 ± 0.0156

^aEach set was composed of 100 samples differing in the configuration of 40 charges generated from a uniform distribution.

^b"W," "M," and "S" denote "weak," "moderate," and "strong" electric fields, respectively.

FIG. 2. Performance of the distributed DMS tensors of ground-state water molecule in strong non-uniform electric field. In this Figure, “*Ab initio* DMS” [panels (a), (d), and (g)] refers to the model from Eq. (23) and “Generalized DMS” [panels (b), (e), and (h)] refers to the generalized model with $R_{\max} = 2$ where R_{\max} is the maximum power in the expansion from Eq. (25). Comparison with the distributed dipole-dipole polarizability model is also shown in this figure in panels (c), (f), and (i). The ensemble of electric fields corresponds to the “S” set from Tables I and II.

Similarly as in the uniform electric field, the *ab initio* DMS model from Eq. (23) as well as the generalized linear DMS model is insufficient to correctly describe the polarization energy in the non-uniform electric field, although the correlation with the benchmark is still very clear with a slope of ~ 2 [Fig. 2(a)]. Again, induced dipole moments are reproduced very well also in strong electric fields [RMSD of 44.8 mD and lesser, $R^2 > 96\%$; Figs. 2(d) and 2(e)]. Induced quadrupole moments are well described only by the generalized DMS model. For example, in moderate electric fields, RMSQ is $10.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ D}\text{\AA}$ with $R^2 = 93.7\%$, whereas the *ab initio* DMS model yields RMSQ of $28.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ D}\text{\AA}$ ($R^2 = 53.9\%$).

The most sophisticated model studied in this work, the generalized quadratic DMS model, yields excellent predic-

tions of the polarization energies and induced multipole moments in all strengths of the non-uniform electric field tested. The errors in predicting polarization energy are reduced by over an order of magnitude when compared with the linear DMS models. Improvement of accuracy can also be observed in the case of induced multipole moment predictions, but the effect is less significant. What is particularly interesting is that in weak and moderate electric fields, the generalized quadratic DMS model performs better than the distributed dipole-dipole polarizability model, whereas only in strong electric fields the situation is reversed [RMSE of 0.402, $R^2 = 97.2\%$, and 0.332 kcal/mol, $R^2 = 98.1\%$ for the DMS and polarizability model, respectively; see also Figs. 2(b) and 2(c)]. Nevertheless, the quadratic DMS model yields still very accurate predictions of

polarization energy and induced multipole moments, even in the strong electric field.

Recently, it was found by Fried *et al.*, by performing molecular dynamics simulations with a classical polarizable force field, that the average electric field experienced by a water molecule in the liquid phase in room temperature is around 0.014 a.u. (~ 70 MV/cm).⁴¹ This value corresponds to our moderate electric field set of samples (denoted as “M” in Tables I and II) for which the accuracy of the generalized quadratic DMS model is excellent. Water molecules can experience stronger electric fields in certain geometries of hydrogen bonded clusters, even up to 0.055 a.u. according to the study by Reischl *et al.*⁴² This electric field magnitude falls into our strong electric field regime (denoted as “S”) in which the generalized quadratic DMS model still provides accurate predictions [see also error distributions in Figs. 2(b), 2(e), and 2(h)]. Therefore, it is believed that the generalized quadratic DMS model is capable of accurately describing the polarization of the ground-state water molecule in inhomogeneous electric fields that are comparable in strength to condensed phase conditions.

C. Computational cost and automatization of the generalized DMS model

Although the cost of computation of the perturbed one-electron density matrices from the generalized DMS tensors and the distribution of the electric field is negligible, obtaining the generalized DMS tensors for a particular molecule involves a substantial amount of full QM calculations. This is, however, a relatively expensive operation that has to be performed only once when the EFP-like strategy is adopted. Note also that each of such preparatory calculations is an independent computational task, and hence, its automatization and parallelization is straightforward. Moreover, the implementation of the method does not depend on the level of theory because only the perturbed density matrices are needed. The least-squares fit, i.e., the computation of the gradient and Hessian matrix including its inversion, is inexpensive. This step can be implemented in an independent script or program taking as input the perturbed density matrices obtained by using any available quantum chemistry package. Therefore, the linear regression method to obtain the DMS tensors could be applied to any molecular fragment at a chosen level of theory in a fairly black box manner, provided that the one-particle density matrices are available. In the illustrations shown in this work, a set of 100 independent full QM calculations was sufficient to get statistically relevant set of perturbed ground state density matrices.

V. SUMMARY AND A FEW CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this work, it was demonstrated that the generalized DMS models from Eq. (25) can accurately describe the polarization-induced deformation of the one-particle ground-state electronic density due to the uniform and non-uniform distribution of the electric field. It was also shown that the accuracy of the model can be improved by extending the parameter space of the susceptibility tensors. Even at the current state of

development, the generalized quadratic DMS model is of comparable and quantitative energetic accuracy as the distributed polarizability model (RMSE of 0.4 kcal/mol in strong electric fields and less than 0.06 kcal/mol in moderate and weak fields). Moreover, any type of one-particle density matrix could be treated by using generalized DMS models, which is much more difficult to realize when a conventional multipole model is used. Therefore, it is believed that the generalized DMS approach has an important advantage over the multipole-based approach, i.e., it provides more detailed tensor description of the spatial polarization of the electron density distribution, which could be combined, for example, with density-based methods of interaction energy calculations.²⁶

It is anticipated here that the generalized models from Eq. (25) should be studied in the future with an emphasis on their further optimization and application for molecular aggregates. For this purpose, more general forms of Eq. (25), as well as the choice of distributed sites should be further investigated, preferably considering post-Hartree-Fock methods and electronically excited states. Nevertheless, owing to the capability of the proposed approach to correctly capture the polarization of the ground state’s electron density, the generalized density matrix susceptibility tensors could be used in accurate fragment-based calculations of extended molecular aggregates described at correlated levels of theory, particularly including the excited state chemistry.

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APPENDIX A: ORIGIN-INDEPENDENCE OF THE INDUCED DIPOLE MOMENT

Multipole one-electron integrals depend on the origin with respect to which they are evaluated. However, the induced dipole moment defined in Eq. (15) has to be origin-independent. Denoting the overlap AO integrals by $S_{\alpha\beta} = \langle \alpha | \beta \rangle$, it follows that $\mathbb{M}_u(\mathbf{r}_Q) = \mathbb{M}_u(\mathbf{0}) - u_Q \mathbf{S}$ for $u = x, y, z$. Thus,

$$\mathbb{L}_u(\mathbf{r}_Q) = \mathbb{L}_u(\mathbf{0}) - u_Q \mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)}), \quad (\text{A1})$$

where

$$\mathbb{L}_u(\mathbf{0}) = \mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot \mathbb{M}_u(\mathbf{0}) \cdot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)}). \quad (\text{A2})$$

But

$$\mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{D}^{(0)}) = \mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{1}) \quad (\text{A3})$$

since $\mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger} \cdot \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{C}^{(0)} = \mathbf{1}$. In the simplest case of $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{1}$ (i.e., the AO basis functions are orthogonal), $\mathbb{L}_u(\mathbf{r}_Q) = \mathbb{L}_u(\mathbf{0})$ which guarantees charge conservation. When a non-orthogonal AO basis is used, the following general condition must be satisfied:

$$\Re\left\{\text{Tr}\left[\delta\mathbf{C}\cdot\mathbf{C}^{(0)\dagger}\cdot(\mathbf{S}-\mathbf{1})\right]\right\}=0. \quad (\text{A4})$$

Due to the fact that Λ considered here is accurate only up to first-order, the above expression is not valid. Therefore, the polarization-induced distributed dipole moments defined in Eq. (15) are exactly origin-independent as long as the AO basis is orthogonalized. In such a case, one can compute one-electron dipole integrals with respect to any origin and the resulting susceptibilities $\mathbb{B}^{(i;1)}$ from Eq. (24) will be uniquely defined. They can be back-transformed to the original (non-orthogonal) AO basis, $\mathbf{X}\cdot\mathbb{B}^{(i;1)}\cdot\mathbf{X}$, where \mathbf{X} is an orthogonalizer. The numerical tests confirmed that $\text{Tr}[\delta\mathbf{D}\cdot\mathbf{S}]\sim 10^{-16}$ with $\delta\mathbf{D}$ given by Eq. (23) and susceptibilities transformed to the non-orthogonal AO basis.

APPENDIX B: EXPLICIT FORMULAE FOR GRADIENT AND HESSIAN BLOCKS IN LINEAR REGRESSION DMS MODEL

The gradient vector \mathbf{g} and the Hessian matrix \mathbf{H} are built from blocks associated with a particular type of parameters, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{g}=\begin{pmatrix}\mathbf{g}^{[11]} \\ \mathbf{g}^{[2]} \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{H}=\begin{pmatrix}\mathbf{H}^{[11]} & \mathbf{H}^{[12]} \\ \mathbf{H}^{[21]} & \mathbf{H}^{[22]} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{B1})$$

where the block indices 1 and 2 correspond to the first- and second-order susceptibilities, respectively. Note that the second derivatives of $\delta D^{(N)}$ with respect to the adjustable parameters vanish due to the linear functional form of Eq. (27). Thus, the gradient element of the r th block and the Hessian element of the (rs) th block read

$$g^{[r]}\equiv\frac{\partial Z}{\partial s^{[r]}}=-2\sum_N\overline{\delta D}^{(N)}\frac{\partial[\delta D^{(N)}]}{\partial s^{[r]}}, \quad (\text{B2a})$$

$$H^{[rs]}\equiv\frac{\partial^2 Z}{\partial s^{[r]}\partial s^{[s]}}=2\sum_N\frac{\partial[\delta D^{(N)}]}{\partial s^{[r]}}\frac{\partial[\delta D^{(N)}]}{\partial s^{[s]}}. \quad (\text{B2b})$$

The explicit formulae for the gradient are

$$g_{ku}^{[1]}=-2\sum_N\overline{\delta D}^{(N)}F_{ku}^{(N)}, \quad (\text{B3a})$$

$$g_{kuw}^{[2]}=-2r_{uw}\sum_N\overline{\delta D}^{(N)}F_{ku}^{(N)}F_{kw}^{(N)}. \quad (\text{B3b})$$

The Hessian subsequently follows to be

$$H_{ku,lw}^{[11]}=2\sum_NF_{ku}^{(N)}F_{lw}^{(N)}, \quad (\text{B4a})$$

$$H_{ku,lu'w'}^{[12]}=2r_{u'w'}\sum_NF_{ku}^{(N)}F_{lu'}^{(N)}F_{lw'}^{(N)}, \quad (\text{B4b})$$

$$H_{kuw,lu'w'}^{[22]}=2r_{uw}r_{u'w'}\sum_NF_{ku}^{(N)}F_{kw}^{(N)}F_{lu'}^{(N)}F_{lw'}^{(N)}. \quad (\text{B4c})$$

Note that due to the symmetry of the Hessian matrix, the block 21 is a transpose of the block 12. The composite indices ku and kuw are constructed from the distributed site index k and the appropriate symmetry-adapted ($w < u$) Cartesian component of a particular DMS tensor: u for the

first-order and uw for the second-order susceptibility tensor, respectively. The method described above can be easily extended to third and higher orders.

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